

Use of the Indirect Photoluminescence Peak as an Optical Probe of Interface Defectivity in MoS₂

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Defect characterization of 2D materials is a critical aspect for their successful integration in future electronic devices. Here, a simple characterization technique is proposed that opens a path for fast, non-invasive, quality assessment of transition metal dichalcogenide (TMDC) layers, such as MoS₂, and their interfaces. It relates to the correlation between substrate-induced traps and the indirect-to-direct photoluminescence peak ratio. It is shown that the indirect peak is quenched when interfacial trap sites are present. A physical mechanism is proposed to explain the observations based on different recombination mechanisms.

1 Introduction

One of the challenges existing for 2D materials is the fast and non-invasive assessment of material quality or defectivity^{1,2}. An important milestone for large scale integration of materials in a semiconductor production process is the development of in-line metrology techniques, able to assess the material quality, from growth to integration. This is currently not available for two-dimensional materials, as characterization techniques often require the fabrication of complex test structures. Here, we propose an analysis technique which can give insight in the trap density inside the MoS₂ bandgap, while being non-invasive and fast.

One of the factors that can strongly influence the performance of 2D materials, is the substrate interaction. For both graphene and transition metal dichalcogenides (TMDCs), it has been shown^{3,4,5,6,7,8} that amorphous dielectric substrates such as SiO₂ cause increased scattering, while enhanced performance is achieved when atomically flat 2D materials, such as hexagonal boron nitride (hBN), are employed as substrates. Performance, however, is often measured from devices, where mobility, hysteresis or interface trap density (D_{IT}) are assessed. This requires full device processing before the metrics can be acquired, where such processing can introduce non-idealities in the material which are difficult to deconvolve using electrical measurements^{9,10,11,12}. This strongly supports the need for characterization techniques and metrics which can correlate material and interface quality before any processing takes place or/and between fabrication steps. For the case of graphene and carbon nanotubes, Raman spectroscopy is a powerful in-line quality assessment tool, with information on defectivity, flatness, thickness, etc^{13,14,15}. The same fast and non-invasive quality metrics are not mature for the case of 2D TMDCs. One technique which can potentially fill this role is photoluminescence (PL) spectroscopy.

Several works have used photoluminescence to study the properties of the interface between 2D TMDC and different substrates, with particular focus on the direct photoluminescence peak from monolayers, arising from direct radiative transitions from the conduction band to the valence band^{16,17,18,19}. The direct photoluminescence peak of MoS₂, around 1.8 eV, contains information on thickness, doping and strain^{20,21,22}. Additionally, direct exciton lifetime measurements can give insights on interface scattering and defect dynamics^{23,24}. However, as thickness increases above the monolayer limit, the direct bandgap of MoS₂ transitions to an indirect bandgap. Notably, not much attention has been given to the peak originating from indirect bandgap transitions, present in thicker layers (≥ 2 monolayers)²⁰. From a technological perspective, thicker layers have a series of advantages compared to monolayers: their lower volume-to-surface ratio makes them more tolerant towards ambient or process-induced degradation²⁵; their smaller bandgap results in higher current density and lower contact resistance^{26,27,28}. Here, we investigate the behavior of the indirect PL peak in multilayer MoS₂ as a function of the substrate, and suggest it as simple and sensitive metric to qualitatively assess interface trap density. We show that the indirect peak is quenched, depending on the substrate interaction, and in the presence of interface trapped species. We attribute this quenching to interface traps acting as recombination centers in the bandgap of MoS₂, and discuss the underlying physics of this observation. We propose the indirect-to-direct PL peak intensity ratio as a material and interface quality metric.

2 Results and discussion

2.1 Influence of the substrate

We assemble ultra-clean hBN/5ML MoS₂/hBN and hBN/5ML MoS₂/SiO₂ structures as described in the methods section by picking up a suitable MoS₂ flake with hBN and placing the stack on a second hBN flake^{3,5}. We start by identifying a flake which lies partially outside the bottom hBN flake – thus on SiO₂ – and partially inside, on hBN. Figure 1a shows the optical image (taken in differential interference contrast (DIC) mode) of the region of interest in the 5ML MoS₂ flake, where the red region is completely encapsulated in hBN and the light-yellow regions (pointed by arrows) only have hBN on top, and the substrate is SiO₂. The single crystalline and uniformly thick flake allows the assumption that all changes observed originate from the surrounding environment, not from non-uniformities in the flake itself. The thick (20nm) bottom hBN flake allows the assumption of a high quality, atomically flat interface formed with MoS₂²⁹. PL is acquired in both regions and shown in Figure 1b. The most important difference between the two is the strong reduction of the peak at 1.37 eV. This low energy peak originates from indirect radiative transitions in the 5ML MoS₂ flake, while the peak around 1.8 eV originates from direct transitions²⁰. We confirm this observation by performing a measurement map in the whole region and by plotting the relative intensity of the peaks in Figure 1c. The heatmap shows that the intensity ratio between indirect and direct peak (I_{ind}/I_{dir}) clearly reduces when the MoS₂ flake lies on SiO₂. On hBN, both direct and indirect peak are high, but on SiO₂, the indirect peak significantly reduces. Beyond the clear reduction in the indirect photoluminescence peak, changes in strain and doping distributions also occur depending on the substrate material, as from the Raman mapping of the same region, shown as a strain/doping plot in Figure S1.

We now expand this analysis to two additional substrates, sapphire and HfO₂. The indirect-to-direct PL peak intensity ratio (I_{ind}/I_{dir}) of multiple flakes on each of the substrates is presented in Figure 2, as a function of the median substrate roughness, extracted from atomic force microscope (AFM) images. We observe that in neither case the indirect PL is as high as when MoS₂ lies on hBN. We consider that there might be a complex correlation with at least three factors: surface roughness, surface chemistry of the target substrate, and presence of interfacial species between the substrate and the 2D material. This will be addressed in the next section. Additionally, part of the flakes presented in Figure 2 do not have top hBN encapsulation. This has minor or no impact on the I_{ind}/I_{dir} of MoS₂, as seen in Figure S2 of the Supporting Information.

2.2 Physical mechanism

2.2.1 Recombination mechanisms and photoluminescence intensity

When light is irradiated on a 2D semiconducting film, electron-hole pairs – excitons – are generated by an electron being excited from the valence band to the conduction band, given that the photon energy of the light source is in excess of the bandgap of the 2D semiconducting film. Once generated, the electron-hole pair can recombine again through 3 mechanisms: Radiative, Shockley-Read-Hall (SRH) or Auger recombination^{30,31,32}. Although defects inside the bandgap might result in detectable photoluminescence peaks, under very specific conditions^{33,34}, it is much more common that they contribute to reducing the emitted radiation, through non-radiative recombination. In 2D TMDCs, defect-assisted Auger recombination is the main non-radiative decay path for excitons, competing with radiative recombination^{35,23,24,36}. Furthermore, surface recombination through defect states dominates the carrier lifetime²⁴. Figure 3 schematically represents radiative recombination (a), “traditional” Auger recombination (b) and defect-assisted Auger recombination (c)

For the first mechanism, radiative recombination (Fig 3a), the exciton will recombine by emitting a photon with an energy equal to that of the transport bandgap of the semiconductor minus the binding energy of the exciton. “Traditional” Auger recombination (Fig 3b) is the recombination of the exciton where the excess energy is transferred to a neighboring electron (or hole) which moves to a higher energy state. Defect-assisted Auger recombination (Fig 3c) occurs when the carriers recombine through mid-gap traps present in the structure and the excess energy is transferred to a third carrier that is excited to a higher energy level. In contrast to traditional semiconductors, strong Coulomb interactions in two-dimensional atomic materials, together with strong electron and hole correlations in 2D TMDCs, make Auger processes effective for capturing carriers by traps in the bandgap²³. Defect-assisted Auger recombination becomes the main non-radiative recombination pathway in MoS₂²³. It depends both on the trap density and on the carrier concentration. The summary of the mechanisms can be given in terms of the exciton decay. Once the TMDC is irradiated by a laser, a number of excitons N_0 is generated. These excitons decay over time, according to¹⁶

$$N(t) = \frac{N_0 e^{-t/\tau_{tot}}}{\frac{1}{2} (1 + \gamma N_0 (1 - e^{-t/\tau_{tot}}))}, \quad (1)$$

where γ is the Auger rate^{23,16}, defined as $\gamma = B n_d (1 - F_d)$, with B an Auger constant, n_d the trap density and F_d the Fermi distribution. τ_{tot} is defined according to $1/\tau_{tot} = 1/\tau_{rad}^{eff} + 1/\tau_{nr}$, where τ_{rad}^{eff} is the effective radiative lifetime and τ_{nr} the non-radiative lifetime¹⁶, which depends on the carrier concentration and on the trap density. By integrating the exciton decay over time, the photoluminescence intensity I_{PL} of each of the two peaks can be obtained, by

$$I_{PL} = \frac{A}{\tau_{rad}^{eff}} \int_{t=0}^{t=\tau_{tot}} N(t) dt = \frac{2A}{\gamma} \times \frac{\tau_{tot}}{\tau_{rad}^{eff}} \times (0.45 + \ln(\gamma N_0)), \quad (2)$$

where A is a factor to take into account the effect of self absorption and reflection of internally generated photons, and is treated as a constant as a function of time³¹.

For direct bandgap semiconductors, radiative recombination can easily dominate over defect-assisted mechanisms, since only a photon is needed for the excitons to decay. Thus, the total recombination is dominated by photon emission and it is not so strongly affected by trap densities, unless a very high amount of traps is present – in which case Auger dominates²⁴.

For indirect bandgap semiconductors, the opposite is true. In this case, defect-assisted recombination will be the most important recombination mechanism, since both photons and phonons are needed for radiative recombination. However, if the trap density is low enough, the radiative recombination can still be in the same order of the non-radiative carrier recombination. This condition will lead to the appearance of a distinct indirect photoluminescence peak, as observed experimentally in Fig. 1c, where MoS₂ is on a quasi-ideal interface. Indeed, it has been reported that the MoS₂/hBN interface has one order of magnitude less trapped charge density than the MoS₂/SiO₂ one³⁷, being as low as $5.2 \times 10^9 \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ eV}^{-1}$ in some reports³⁸.

The mechanism is schematically represented in Fig 4. In the next section we will discuss the comparison between the photoluminescence intensity coming from each of the transitions – direct and indirect – and the validity of using the I_{ind}/I_{dir} ratio.

2.2.2 Direct vs indirect PL and I_{ind}/I_{dir} ratio

If photons with energy larger than both direct and indirect gaps are pumped, electrons are excited not only to the smaller indirect transition (between K and Γ) but also to the larger direct transition (K-K). This is the case for the 532 nm (2.33 eV) laser used in this study. Thus, both recombination pathways will occur at the same time. Due to the requirement of a phonon to conserve momentum, the radiative recombination on the indirect transition will be inefficient and sensitive to traps, while the recombination from the electrons in the direct transition will be very efficient.

Due to the requirement for conservation of momentum, the radiative lifetime of an indirect semiconductor can be significantly larger than that of a direct semiconductor. For MoS₂, it was found that the radiative recombination lifetime from bulk material is 2.6 ns while from monolayers it is 800 ps³⁹. A similar case is observed for other TMDCs, such as WS₂, where a trilayer sample has radiative lifetime more than 60 times longer than a monolayer sample⁴⁰. This derives from the much smaller radiative recombination coefficients of indirect semiconductors, compared to direct³¹. The non-radiative lifetime, on the other hand, depends on the properties of the traps²³, and can be assumed constant for both direct and indirect gaps. As such, the total recombination time (τ_{tot}) can be dominated by radiative recombination for the direct transition, while in the indirect transition non-radiative recombination competes with radiative.

As seen before, the photoluminescence intensity depends on the effective radiative lifetime τ_{rad}^{eff} , the number of photogenerated excitons N_0 , the total lifetime τ_{tot} and the Auger rate γ . The photoluminescence intensity can be described by

$$I_{PL} = \frac{2A}{\gamma} \times \frac{\tau_{tot}}{\tau_{rad}^{eff}} \times (0.45 + \ln(\gamma N_0)). \quad (3)$$

Furthermore, we should now consider the validity of using the indirect-to-direct PL peak ratio across different substrates to assess the interface defectivity. For this purpose, we consider the two peaks separately, I_{ind} and I_{dir} , and each of those is described by its own equation such as Eq. 3. The ratio of these two can be described as shown by

$$\frac{I_{ind}}{I_{dir}} \propto \frac{\frac{2A_{ind}}{\gamma_{ind}} \times \frac{\tau_{tot-ind}}{\tau_{rad-ind}^{eff}} \times (0.45 + \ln(\gamma_{ind} N_{0-ind}))}{\frac{2A_{dir}}{\gamma_{dir}} \times \frac{\tau_{tot-dir}}{\tau_{rad-dir}^{eff}} \times (0.45 + \ln(\gamma_{dir} N_{0-dir}))}. \quad (4)$$

By assuming that A is constant for both peaks when the same material lies on the same substrate, and that the number of injected excitons is the same in both peaks, we can simplify Equation 4 to

$$\frac{I_{ind}}{I_{dir}} \propto \frac{\gamma_{dir}}{\gamma_{ind}} \times \frac{\tau_{tot-ind} \tau_{rad-dir}^{eff}}{\tau_{rad-ind}^{eff} \tau_{tot-dir}} \times \frac{(0.45 + \ln(\gamma_{ind} N_0))}{(0.45 + \ln(\gamma_{dir} N_0))}. \quad (5)$$

We now have two parts of the equation that depend on γ_{ind} and γ_{dir} , and one part which depends on the lifetimes of radiative and non-radiative recombination. We can assume that the experimentally observed dependence of $\frac{I_{ind}}{I_{dir}}$ with the substrate mainly originates from this third factor. This results in

$$\frac{I_{ind}}{I_{dir}} \propto \frac{\tau_{tot-ind} \tau_{rad-dir}^{eff}}{\tau_{rad-ind}^{eff} \tau_{tot-dir}}. \quad (6)$$

For the case of the direct photoluminescence peak, the direct exciton decay means that the total exciton lifetime $\tau_{tot-dir}$ is much closer to the radiative lifetime $\tau_{rad-dir}^{eff}$ than in the case of phonon-assisted indirect transitions. Again, we can simplify Equation 6 considering that $\tau_{tot-dir}$ tends to $\tau_{rad-dir}^{eff}$, which results in Equation 7, where $1/\tau_{tot} = 1/\tau_{rad}^{eff} + 1/\tau_{Auger}$.

$$\frac{I_{ind}}{I_{dir}} \alpha \frac{\tau_{tot-ind}}{\tau_{rad-ind}^{eff}} = \frac{\tau_{rad-ind}^{eff} \tau_{Auger-ind}}{\tau_{rad-ind}^{eff} + \tau_{Auger-ind}} \times \frac{1}{\tau_{rad-ind}^{eff}} \quad (7)$$

Finally, by substituting $\tau_{Auger-ind}$ by the definition of Auger lifetime of $\tau_{Auger} = 1/Bn_dN^2(1-F_d)^{23}$ it can be seen the dependence of the I_{ind}/I_{dir} ratio and the trap density n_d , in Equation 8. While $\tau_{rad-ind}^{eff}$ remains constant for the same material, the I_{ind}/I_{dir} ratio increases as the trap density n_d reduces, confirming qualitatively the experimental observations of high I_{ind}/I_{dir} ratio when MoS₂ lies on hBN and low ratio on SiO₂ and other defective substrates.

$$\frac{I_{ind}}{I_{dir}} \alpha \frac{\tau_{Auger-ind}}{\tau_{rad-ind}^{eff} + \tau_{Auger-ind}} = \frac{1}{\tau_{rad-ind}^{eff} Bn_d N^2 (1 - F_d) + 1} \quad (8)$$

In summary, the I_{ind}/I_{dir} ratio is a simple metric to assess the trap density, which allows a simplified analysis of the recombination mechanisms, and ultimately depends on simple factors of the radiative lifetime and trap density.

2.2.3 Origin of traps

To result in the observed quenching of indirect PL, the energy of the interface traps has to overlap with the bandgap of MoS₂. If (1) the trap density is reduced, or (2) the middle of the bandgap is not aligned with the traps, then the effect they have on the 2D material can be decreased. For example, if the traps are located on an energy level higher than the conduction band of the TMDC, they can result in electron doping, if they are located lower than the valence band, they can result in hole doping, or have minimal effect. If, however, they overlap with the forbidden gap, they will result in electron/hole trapping, which, in MOSFETs, electrically translates as an increase in hysteresis and degraded subthreshold slope. Optically, however, traps overlapping with the bandgap will act as recombination centers for excitons and trions. These recombination centers will have stronger effect on indirect transitions, which rely on the presence of a phonon and a photon than on direct transitions which only emit a photon. This explains why different substrates strongly affect the *indirect* photoluminescence peak, while the *direct* peak remains less affected.

The physical origin of these traps, however, is still under study. Traditionally, the energy and density of interface traps is measured from covalently bonded metal-oxide-semiconductor (MOS) structures. In this case, SiO₂ is known to have two defect bands, one 2.6 eV below the conduction band, and another at 4.6 eV⁴¹. Similarly, HfO₂ is known to have at least one band of defects 2 eV below the conduction band edge⁴². For 2D materials, the structure can become more complex. Since 2D materials are exfoliated or transferred onto surfaces and are only weakly bonded to them, they allow the presence of interfacial species – water, hydrocarbons – depending on which substrate they are onto^{43,38}. Additionally, the polar OH groups present on the oxide surface are proposed to lead to dipole formation and possibly midgap traps in transferred MoS₂^{44,45}. Silanol groups cannot be removed solely by typical low temperature anneals and/or cleans done before transferring 2D materials⁴⁶. In traditional layer growth process, such as SiO₂ on Si, on the other hand, the starting *surface* is converted to a covalently bonded *interface*, through high temperature and chemical processes. This interface is largely free of trapped species and OH groups, in contrast with the weakly bonded van der Waals “interface” between 2D materials and their substrates. Lastly, the surface roughness of the underlying substrate can result in non uniform strain, which leads to bandgap modifications in thin TMDCs, and is proposed to cause the appearance of hole traps^{47,6}.

In this context, if we turn back our attention to Figure 2, we observe that MoS₂ on hBN has the highest indirect-to-direct PL ratio, and thus the lowest density of defects overlapping with the MoS₂ forbidden gap. hBN forms self-cleaning interfaces with other 2D materials^{43,38} – so no water and hydrocarbons –, it is self-passivated – so no dangling bonds or OH groups –, and atomically flat – so the lowest surface roughness⁴⁸. Sapphire, on its turn, is almost atomically flat, but has both OH groups and allows the presence of interfacial species in the interface with MoS₂. Accordingly, the I_{ind}/I_{dir} PL peak ratio reduces when MoS₂ flakes are on sapphire substrates. Lastly, both thermal SiO₂ and ALD HfO₂ present all three characteristics, interfacial species, silanol groups and higher levels of surface roughness. As observed

in Figure 2, the I_{ind}/I_{dir} PL peak ratio reduces even further when MoS₂ flakes are exfoliated on these substrates. When considering the differences between SiO₂ and HfO₂, it is important to consider the higher defect densities and different defect band position of this carbon-based ALD oxide, compared to thermal SiO₂⁴². This, allied with higher surface roughness, is considered to be the main reason for the additional quenching of the indirect PL peak, when MoS₂ is on HfO₂.

To try to de-convolute these three factors, we proceed to study the isolated effect of interfacial species, when the substrate is kept constant. For this, we focus on the bubbles – water, air and hydrocarbons segregated into localized positions⁴³, – formed between MoS₂ and hBN, when fabricating the hBN/MoS₂/hBN heterostructures.

2.3 Influence of interfacial species

As seen from other reports^{49,38,29}, trapped species in heterostructures introduce scattering and degradation of the electrical properties. We assume this is linked to electron or hole traps, and following the physical mechanism proposed, would also result in a selective reduction of the indirect PL peak.

Thus, to further support our analysis, we take a closer look at the impact of trapped species inside the heterostructures. Trapped species can be water, air, or hydrocarbons trapped between the different layers^{50,43,51}. For that, we select a region of a hBN/MoS₂/hBN structure with strong incidence of trapped species, seen as bubbles in the AFM topography in figure 5a. This is an interesting case, since the substrate is the same in all cases, hBN, but foreign species are present in localized positions. A PL map is done on the same area, and the heatmap of the direct/indirect PL peak intensity ratio is presented in figure 5b. It can be observed that the ratio reduces roughly in correspondence to the location of the bubbles, supporting our observation of selective quenching of the indirect peak in more defective regions. The percentage of bubbles in the AFM map is 18%, while there are 31% of I_{ind}/I_{dir} values below the median and standard deviation of a flat region. We attribute the discrepancies in values to the limited spot size of our system and the interference of different regions.

The trapped species not only introduce a local defect, but also localized strain (due to bending), which in turn leads to bandgap changes in the 2D material. At this point, however, the individual impact of each aspect on the indirect photoluminescence cannot be deconvoluted. Nonetheless, both result in disorder in the structure, and this disorder leads to the observation above. The position of the PL peaks (Supporting Information S3), however, is not significantly changed, and neither of the Raman E_{2g}¹ out-of-plane mode (Supporting Information Figure S4), indicating that strain and bandgap modifications are not the dominating effects^{22,52}.

3 Conclusion

In summary, we have investigated the modulation of the indirect photoluminescence peak in MoS₂ flakes on different substrates. We have observed that this peak is reduced when MoS₂ is supported by more interacting substrates, such as SiO₂, while it shows high intensity in less interacting interfaces with hBN. By correlating AFM and PL maps, it is demonstrated that this peak is also quenched in correlation with trapped species in hBN/MoS₂/hBN heterostructures. We describe and discuss the physical mechanism which results in these observations. This work emphasizes that the indirect-to-direct photoluminescence peak ratio of MoS₂ can be used as a fast and non-invasive technique, which can potentially be included in-line for probing material (intrinsic or contamination-related) and interface defective trap states. This technique can also be expanded to other 2D TMDCs with similar band structure, such as WS₂, where the same scattering mechanisms are present.

4 Methods

4.1 Substrates and cleans

2-inch epi-ready double-side polished sapphire substrates from Roditi are used. The substrates are c-plane oriented with a miscut angle of 0 degree \pm 0.1 degree. They are characterized by an atomically smooth surface showing the typical step-and-terrace-like structure⁵³.

From the Si substrate, SiO₂ is grown thermally to a thickness of 90 nm. The backside of the wafer is etched using HF. 10 nm HfO₂ is deposited by atomic layer deposition (ALD), using Tetrakis(ethylmethyamido)hafnium (TEMAH) and H₂O precursors, at 250 °C in a Savannah reactor. hBN flakes are exfoliated from crystals grown by chemical vapor transport using high purity precursors⁵⁴.

Sapphire wafers are cleaned using a 3:1 concentrated acid mixture of H₂SO₄:H₃PO₄ at 300 °C for 20 min to obtain an OH terminated surface⁵⁵. SiO₂ and HfO₂ substrates are cleaned by diluted SC1 clean (20:1:1: mixture of H₂O:H₂O₂:NH₄OH) for 15 minutes at room temperature, followed by a water rinse, also to obtain an OH terminated surface. hBN and MoS₂ flakes are not cleaned, since the exfoliation results in cleavage of the vdW-bonded layers and thus a clean surface with no residues.

4.2 Structure fabrication

MoS₂ flakes are exfoliated on SiO₂ and thin uniform flakes are identified. hBN flakes are similarly exfoliated on Si₂, and in this case large uniform flakes with \sim 20 nm thickness are identified as the bottom hBN. The top hBN flakes is directly exfoliated on a PVA/PMMA polymer stamp, and used to pickup a suitable MoS₂ flake. The hBN/MoS₂ structure is then put in contact with a suitable hBN flake on SiO₂ and the polymer is removed from the stack. Water (2 hours), acetone (5 minutes), isopropanol (dip) and dichloromethane (10 minutes) are used to remove the polymer residues remaining on top of the heterostructure. The MoS₂ flake is protected from the impact of water by the hBN encapsulation. A 200 °C vacuum anneal for 2h further increases the MoS₂/hBN interaction.

4.3 Photoluminescence measurements

Photoluminescence (PL) spectra are collected in a confocal Raman microscopic system, using exciting lasers with primary wavelength of 532 nm (green). The laser radiation is focused onto the MoS₂ sheets using a 100x objective lens with a spot-size around 1 μ m. Photoluminescence spectra are resolved by a spectrometer using gratings of 600 mm⁻¹ and acquired by an CCD detector. Measurements are performed at room temperature, in air. Mappings are performed by stepping the stage in steps of 400 nm in the X and Y directions, and recording one spectrum at each step.

Supporting Information

Supporting Information is available from the Wiley Online Library or from the author.

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References

- [1] IRDS, *International Roadmap for Devices and Systems: 2017 Edition*, IEEE, **2018**.
- [2] G. V. Resta, A. Leonhardt, Y. Balaji, S. De Gendt, P.-E. Gaillardon, G. De Micheli, *IEEE Transactions on Very Large Scale Integration (VLSI) Systems* **2019**, *27*, 7 1.

- [3] L. Banszerus, M. Schmitz, S. Engels, J. Dauber, M. Oellers, F. Haupt, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, B. Beschoten, C. Stampfer, *Science Advances* **2015**, *1*, 6 e1500222.
- [4] Y. Y. Illarionov, G. Rzepa, M. Walzl, T. Knobloch, A. Grill, M. M. Furchi, T. Mueller, T. Grasser, *2D Materials* **2016**, *3*, 3 1.
- [5] L. Banszerus, H. Janssen, M. Otto, A. Epping, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, B. Beschoten, D. Neumaier, C. Stampfer, *2D Materials* **2017**, *4*, 2.
- [6] M. D. Tran, J. H. Kim, H. Kim, M. H. Doan, D. L. Duong, Y. H. Lee, *ACS Applied Materials and Interfaces* **2018**, *10*, 12 10580.
- [7] Q. A. Vu, S. Fan, S. H. Lee, M.-K. Joo, W. J. Yu, Y. H. Lee, *2D Materials* **2018**, *5*, 3 031001.
- [8] D. Rhodes, S. H. Chae, R. Ribeiro-Palau, J. Hone, *Nature Materials* **2019**, *18*, 6 541.
- [9] C. M. Smyth, R. Addou, S. McDonnell, C. L. Hinkle, R. M. Wallace, Contact metal-MoS₂ interfacial reactions and potential implications on MoS₂-based device performance, **2016**.
- [10] A. Leonhardt, D. Chiappe, I. Asselberghs, C. Huyghebaert, I. Radu, S. De Gendt, *IEEE Electron Device Letters* **2017**, *38*, 11 1606.
- [11] Y. Liu, J. Guo, E. Zhu, L. Liao, S.-J. Lee, M. Ding, I. Shakir, V. Gambin, Y. Huang, X. Duan, *Nature* **2018**, *557*, 7707 696.
- [12] J. Liang, K. Xu, B. Toncini, B. Bersch, B. Jariwala, Y. C. Lin, J. Robinson, S. K. Fullerton-Shirey, *Advanced Materials Interfaces* **2019**, *6*, 3 1801321.
- [13] C. Stampfer, A. Bürli, A. Jungen, C. Hierold, *physica status solidi (b)* **2007**, *244*, 11 4341.
- [14] A. Eckmann, A. Felten, A. Mishchenko, L. Britnell, R. Krupke, K. S. Novoselov, C. Casiraghi **2012**.
- [15] C. Neumann, S. Reichardt, P. Venezuela, M. Drögeler, L. Banszerus, M. Schmitz, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, F. Mauri, B. Beschoten, S. V. Rotkin, C. Stampfer, *Nature Communications* **2015**, *6*, June.
- [16] C. Robert, D. Lagarde, F. Cadiz, G. Wang, B. Lassagne, T. Amand, A. Balocchi, P. Renucci, S. Tongay, B. Urbaszek, X. Marie, *Physical Review B* **2016**, *93*, 20 1.
- [17] Y. Yu, Y. Yu, C. Xu, Y. Q. Cai, L. Su, Y. Zhang, Y. W. Zhang, K. Gundogdu, L. Cao, *Advanced Functional Materials* **2016**, *26*, 26 4733.
- [18] K. F. Mak, J. Shan, *Nature Photonics* **2016**, *10*, 4 216.
- [19] K. Kojima, H. E. Lim, Z. Liu, W. Zhang, T. Saito, Y. Nakanishi, T. Endo, Y. Kobayashi, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, K. Matsuda, Y. Maniwa, Y. Miyauchi, Y. Miyata, *Nanoscale* **2019**, *11*, 27 12798.
- [20] K. F. Mak, C. Lee, J. Hone, J. Shan, T. F. Heinz, *Physical Review Letters* **2010**, *105*, 13 136805.
- [21] K. F. Mak, K. He, C. Lee, G. H. Lee, J. Hone, T. F. Heinz, J. Shan, *Nature Materials* **2013**, *12*, 3 207.
- [22] H. J. Conley, B. Wang, J. I. Ziegler, R. F. Haglund, S. T. Pantelides, K. I. Bolotin, *Nano Letters* **2013**, *13*, 8 3626.
- [23] H. Wang, C. Zhang, F. Rana, *Nano Letters* **2015**, *15*, 1 339.
- [24] H. Wang, C. Zhang, F. Rana, *Nano Letters* **2015**, *15*, 12 8204.
- [25] H. Qiu, L. Pan, Z. Yao, J. Li, Y. Shi, X. Wang, *Cite as: Appl. Phys. Lett* **2012**, *100* 123104.

- [26] H. Zhong, R. Quhe, Y. Wang, Z. Ni, M. Ye, Z. Song, Y. Pan, J. Yang, L. Yang, M. Lei, J. Shi, J. Lu, *Scientific Reports* **2016**, *6*.
- [27] M.-W. Lin, I. I. Kravchenko, J. Fowlkes, X. Li, A. A. Puretzky, C. M. Rouleau, D. B. Geohegan, K. Xiao, *Nanotechnology* **2016**, *27*, 16 165203.
- [28] J. Kwon, J.-Y. Lee, Y.-J. Yu, C.-H. Lee, X. Cui, J. Hone, G.-H. Lee, *Nanoscale* **2017**, *9* 6151.
- [29] D. G. Purdie, N. M. Pugno, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, A. C. Ferrari, A. Lombardo, *Nature Communications* **2018**, *9*, 1 5387.
- [30] W. Shockley, W. T. Read, *Physical Review* **1952**, *87*, 5 835.
- [31] R. Ahrenkiel, *Solid-State Electronics* **1992**, *35*, 3 239 .
- [32] S. M. Sze, *Semiconductor devices: physics and technology*, John wiley & sons, **2008**.
- [33] L. Museur, E. Feldbach, A. Kanaev, *Phys. Rev. B* **2008**, *78* 155204.
- [34] T. T. Tran, C. Zachreson, A. M. Berhane, K. Bray, R. G. Sandstrom, L. H. Li, T. Taniguchi, K. Watanabe, I. Aharonovich, M. Toth, *Phys. Rev. Applied* **2016**, *5* 034005.
- [35] O. Salehzadeh, N. H. Tran, X. Liu, I. Shih, Z. Mi, *Nano Letters* **2014**, *14*, 7 4125.
- [36] P. D. Cunningham, K. M. McCreary, B. T. Jonker, *The journal of physical chemistry letters* **2016**, *7*, 24 5242.
- [37] C. Lee, S. Rathi, M. A. Khan, D. Lim, Y. Kim, S. J. Yun, D. H. Youn, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, G. H. Kim, *Nanotechnology* **2018**, *29*, 33.
- [38] Q. A. Vu, S. Fan, S. H. Lee, M. K. Joo, W. J. Yu, Y. H. Lee, *2D Materials* **2018**, *5*, 3 000000.
- [39] H. Shi, R. Yan, S. Bertolazzi, J. Brivio, B. Gao, A. Kis, D. Jena, H. G. Xing, L. Huang, *ACS Nano* **2013**, *7*, 2 1072.
- [40] L. Yuan, L. Huang, *Nanoscale* **2015**, *7*, 16 7402.
- [41] Y. Y. Illarionov, A. G. Banskchikov, D. K. Polyushkin, S. Wachter, T. Knobloch, M. Thesberg, L. Mennel, M. Paur, M. Stöger-Pollach, A. Steiger-Thirsfeld, et al., *Nature Electronics* **2019**, *1*.
- [42] F. Cerbu, O. Madia, D. V. Andreev, S. Fadida, M. Eizenberg, L. Breuil, J. G. Lisoni, J. A. Kittl, J. Strand, A. L. Shluger, V. V. Afanas'ev, M. Houssa, A. Stesmans, *Applied Physics Letters* **2016**, *108*, 22 222901.
- [43] A. V. Kretinin, Y. Cao, J. S. Tu, G. L. Yu, R. Jalil, K. S. Novoselov, S. J. Haigh, A. Gholinia, A. Mishchenko, M. Lozada, T. Georgiou, C. R. Woods, F. Withers, P. Blake, G. Eda, A. Wirsig, C. Hucho, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, A. K. Geim, R. V. Gorbachev, *Nano Letters* **2014**, *14*, 6 3270.
- [44] V. V. Afanas'ev, D. Chiappe, A. Leonhardt, M. Houssa, C. Huyghebaert, I. Radu, A. Stesmans, *ECS Transactions* **2017**, *80*, 1 191.
- [45] V. V. Afanas'ev, D. Chiappe, M. Perucchini, M. Houssa, C. Huyghebaert, I. Radu, A. Stesmans, *Nanotechnology* **2019**, *30*, 5 055702.
- [46] L. T. Zhuravlev **2000**, *173* 1.
- [47] B. G. Shin, G. H. Han, S. J. Yun, H. M. Oh, J. J. Bae, Y. J. Song, C. Y. Park, Y. H. Lee, *Advanced Materials* **2016**, *28*, 42 9378.
- [48] I. Meric, C. R. Dean, N. Petrone, L. Wang, J. Hone, P. Kim, K. L. Shepard, *Proceedings of the IEEE* **2013**, *101*, 7 1609.

- [49] C. Zheng, Z. Q. Xu, Q. Zhang, M. T. Edmonds, K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, Q. Bao, M. S. Fuhrer, *Nano Letters* **2015**, *15*, 5 3096.
- [50] S. J. Haigh, A. Gholinia, R. Jalil, S. Romani, L. Britnell, D. C. Elias, K. S. Novoselov, L. A. Ponomarenko, A. K. Geim, R. Gorbachev, *Nature Materials* **2012**, *11* 764 EP .
- [51] K. S. Novoselov, A. Mishchenko, A. Carvalho, A. H. Castro Neto, *Science* **2016**, *353*, 6298.
- [52] C. Rice, R. J. Young, R. Zan, U. Bangert, D. Wolverson, T. Georgiou, R. Jalil, K. S. Novoselov, *Physical Review B* **2013**, *87*, 8 081307.
- [53] W. Mortelmans, S. E. Kazzi, A. N. Mehta, D. Vanhaeren, T. Conard, J. Meersschaut, T. Nuytten, S. Degenadt, M. M. Heyns, C. Merckling, *Nanotechnology* **2019**.
- [54] K. Watanabe, T. Taniguchi, H. Kanda, *Nature Materials* **2004**, *3*, 6 404.
- [55] K. Verguts, B. Vermeulen, N. Vrancken, K. Schouteden, C. Van Haesendonck, C. Huyghebaert, M. Heyns, S. De Gendt, S. Brems, *Journal of Physical Chemistry C* **2016**, *120*, 1 297.
- [56] A. Splendiani, L. Sun, Y. Zhang, T. Li, J. Kim, C. Y. Chim, G. Galli, F. Wang, *Nano Letters* **2010**, *10*, 4 1271.

Figure 1: a) Optical micrograph (DIC mode) of hBN/MoS₂/hBN heterostructure. Different materials are outlined and SiO₂/MoS₂/hBN part indicated by arrows. Region used for PL mapping is indicated by the square. b) Photoluminescence spectra of MoS₂ supported by SiO₂ and supported by hBN, showing the direct and indirect radiative transitions. Indirect PL peak is selectively quenched when MoS₂ is on SiO₂, while direct peak remains almost unchanged. c) Heat-map of the ratio between the indirect PL and the direct PL peaks. Indirect PL is strongly quenched where MoS₂ is supported by SiO₂, compared to the hBN region.

Figure 2: Relationship between the indirect/direct PL peak ratio and the surface roughness of different substrates. Indirect PL peak is significantly quenched depending on the substrate the MoS₂ flakes are exfoliated on.

Figure 3: Schematic representation of radiative recombination (a), "traditional" Auger recombination (b) and defect-assisted Auger recombination (c) of excitons in an encapsulated MoS₂ layer.

Figure 4: Schematic band diagram of 4ML-5ML MoS₂⁵⁶ showing the direct and indirect radiative exciton transitions for the case of a “clean” bandgap (electrons are represented in red and holes in white)(a). When traps are present – thin line crossing the middle of the bandgap –, indirect excitons relax predominantly through fast defect-assisted Auger recombination (b). In the second case, the deep defects act as recombination centers, quenching the indirect PL, but since the direct valley has lower radiative lifetime, the direct PL is less impacted by the Auger recombination.

Figure 5: a) AFM topography map of MoS₂ flake encapsulated in hBN, with the occurrence of trapped species in the bottom hBN/MoS₂ interface. b) Corresponding heatmap of the ratio between the indirect PL and the direct PL peaks. Indirect peak is quenched where there are more bubbles.

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Indirect-to-direct photoluminescence peak ratio: A simple, fast and non-invasive method for probing MoS₂ material and interface defective trap states.